

Density, Biomass and Distribution of *Alpheus Macellarius* (Chace, 1988) In Clarin, Bohol

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Abstract:

Alpheus macellarius, locally known as “takla”, is slowly making a round in the fishery industry, as it commands a very good price in the market. Collection of this species is common in the municipality of Clarin, Bohol, where there are six (6) coastal barangays, including Nahawan and Tangaran where collectors frequently visit for collection. The six month collection period started in December 2016 and commenced in May 2017. Three random 25 x 2m radial transects were laid in each sampling site. Density was computed as a number of individuals per m² and biomass, on the other hand, was computed as grams per m². Morisita's Index was used for determining distribution. Density and biomass are higher in Tangaran than Nahawan and yielded a significant difference, using two-way factorial ANOVA, in between barangay and within months. The interaction was also found out in between sites and months. Aggregate distribution was observed in Barangay Tangaran while *A. macellarius* is distributed aggregately and randomly in Nahawan. Since *A. macellarius* are burrowing organisms and can be influenced by different environmental conditions, organic matter of sediment and gut content analysis of the organism may be taken into consideration for future studies, the municipal ordinance may be drafted for regulation purposes and another study of at least 1 year and finally.

Keywords: Aggregate, Random, Takla, Radial transect, Organic matter

CHAPTER I INTRODUCTION

The pistol or snapping shrimp, *Alpheus macellarius* (Chace, 1988) is a decapod known to occur only in some parts of the Philippines namely Bolinao, Pangasinan (Palomar *et al.*, 2004 & 2005), Cebu and Leyte (Chace 1988) and in Calape, Bohol (Rabia *et al.*, 2012). *A. macellarius* is usually found in mangroves and estuarine areas. The collection is usually done manually by tying a hermit crab and using it as a bait and is placed into the burrow until such time that a snapping sound will be heard which signals that *A. macellarius* did gnaw the bait already.

Alpheus macellarius shrimp is locally known as “takla” in Clarin, the northeastern part of Bohol Island. This species is a popular delicacy in the Municipality of Clarin and Calape, Bohol, a neighboring town of Clarin. According to Rabia *et al.* (2012), visitors in Calape would always want to get a taste of this species because of its delicious meat. *A. macellarius* commands a very good price in the market and is sold at ₱150 per kilogram according to the collectors. A typical collector could collect 1-2 kilos per day depending on the weather condition, because according to them, this organism would not come out from its burrow even in the presence of a bait when it is raining. For many years they have been collecting, this quantity in every collection has always been consistent, probably because the method of collecting is not easy to learn and needs honing of skills. Municipality of Clarin has six (6) coastal barangays, of which Nahawan and Tangaran are the barangays frequently visited by native “takla” collectors.

Almeida *et al.* (2010) in their study, make it a point that crustaceans, especially members of the order Decapoda, to which *Alpheus macellarius* belongs, are ecologically and economically important, which prompted scientific studies in many areas including reproduction. The role of the alpheids in reef ecology has been inadequately studied (Banner and Banner, 1971). Burrowing alpheid shrimps, according to Karplus and Thompson (2011), have a mutualistic association between non-burrowing gobiid fishes. The burrow which is constructed and maintained by the shrimp will be used by the goby during the day as a permanent resting place

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overnight and a safe place for breeding. Benthic infauna is known to modify sediment biogeochemistry and stimulate organic matter decomposition, through feeding, burrowing and sediment irrigation (Holmer and Heilskov, 2008). In spite of its apparent economic and ecological importance, *A. macellarius* is a relatively unstudied alpheid species whose distribution has so far been reported only in the Philippines. Palomar *et al.*, (2004 & 2005) recorded *A. macellarius* species in Bolinao, Pangasinan and Chace (1988) in his Albatross Philippine Expedition recorded such species in Cebu Market and Dupon Bay, Leyte. Assessment such as density, biomass and distribution has not been recorded yet. The Municipal Agriculture Office in the municipality of Clarin could provide no available fishery resource data because no Participatory Coastal Resource Assessment or any form of assessment has ever been done in the municipality.

Aside from lack of data, native collectors also complain of the unregulated collection because of foreign collectors from neighboring towns invading and using the detrimental and destructive method of collection. At present, there are efforts deterring the illegal entry of collectors, which involves fines through the Fisherfolk Registration (FishR) of the municipality, according to Cardino and Gulayan (personal communication, June 6, 2016) of the Municipal Agriculture Office-Clarin.

Many crustacean fisheries are artisanal, using static gears, and their socio-economic importance may, therefore, be even greater. This increasing importance requires that stock assessment and management programmes for crustacean fisheries should be effective (Smith and Addison, 2003). The municipal waters of Clarin, although one of the smallest compared to other towns of Bohol province, possesses a high biodiversity potential and is the home of various species of marine flora and fauna (CRM Plan of Clarin 2013-2017). Information on the species density, biomass and distribution in this sense would provide information on the available stock of *Alpheus macellarius* species and further would lead to the knowledge of the species' current status in the fishery resource of the Municipality. Hence, this study.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

This study was conducted to determine density, biomass and distribution of *Alpheus macellarius* (Chace, 1988) in Clarin, Bohol.

1.2. Significance of the Study

This study is of benefit to the following entities:

Stakeholders. For them to be informed of the species importance, and its status in the community for fishery management purpose (open and close season, collection period, size of mature individuals, etc.)

Aquaculturist. Information from this study is essential for developing the aquaculture industry of this species. Aquaculture offers a solution in conserving the population of *A. macellarius* and at the same time, can be a good source of income. In this way, collectors can culture their own stock to meet the demands in the market while allowing the remaining population in the wild to recover.

Students and Researchers. This would pave the way for many studies concerning this species, thereby would contribute to augmenting the amount of literature of *A. macellarius*.

Local Government Unit (LGU) of Clarin. This study would support government regulation of the collection or gathering of this species, thus preventing the reduction of native stocks by means of formulating municipal ordinance.

1.3. Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study deals with the density, biomass and distribution of *Alpheus macellarius* in Clarin, Bohol, specifically in Tangaran and Nahawan. This study was conducted over a six (6) month period from December 2016 – May 2017. The assessment was done only to those barangays where *A. macellarius* was known to exist which was based on the data from the respondents. There was no latest fishery resource survey conducted, thus most of the information gathered was through an interview with the collectors.

1.4. Review of Related Literature

Members of the *Alpheus* and the closely related *Synalpheus* genera, commonly called snapping shrimp, are a ubiquitous component of macrofaunal assemblages in tropical and subtropical shallow-water marine habitats. The snapping shrimp genera are highly speciose: Chace (1988) recognized ~220 species of *Alpheus*

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(24 in the Caribbean; Chace 1972) and ~115 species of *Synalpheus* (Mathew, 2006). This was in consonance to the findings of Williams (1984) as cited by Harikrishnan *et al.* (2010), wherein the snapping shrimps of the family Alpheidae comprise about 425 species with an almost worldwide distribution.

Snapping shrimp are socially monogamous (Nolan and Salmon, 1970; Knowlton & Keller, 1980; Mathews, 2002), and commonly occur in pairs in self-excavated burrows. This species is highly territorial, defending their burrows from all nonpair conspecific or heterospecifics (Mathews, 2002). According to Holmer and Heilskov (2008), the benthic fauna in Bolinao, Pangasinan is visually dominated by the alpheid shrimp *A. macellarius* living in association with the gobiid fishes such as *Cryptocentrus octofasciatus* and *Cryptocentrus singaporensis* generating high mounts on the bottom (Palomar *et al.*, 2004 & 2005). The association between alpheid shrimps and gobiid fishes is widely known in tropical and subtropical environments (Karplus *et al.*, 1974; Yanagasiwa, 1984) and the two species live together in burrows dug by the shrimp and tactile communication is developed between them.

Crustacean fisheries are of global importance because of their high unit value, among others, thus requires effective stock assessment and management programmes (Smith and Addison, 2003). Stock assessment of tropical resources has developed rapidly in the last decade in particular through the work of Pauly (1979, 1980, 1984) and Munro (1983). In fact, according to Garcia (1985), the reason behind the scarce knowledge of the mechanisms of shrimp production and fleet dynamics is the limiting factor of shrimp stock assessment and management and does not appear to be the shortage of methodologies. As to this, Smith and Addison (2003) reviewed and evaluated different methods of stock assessment for crustaceans which involve analytical assessments such as dynamic biomass models, delay-difference models, depletion methods, equilibrium yield and egg per recruit models and dynamic-size structured models.

This study determines *A. macellarius* density, distribution and biomass as to represent indices for stock assessment. Data on density will give a population estimate of the species on a particular site. There will be changes in the density of the species due to natural and human-induced factors (Husson *et al.*, 2009) and thus will play a role in future management actions for the organism in the study. Masterson (2008) cited the study of Nolan and Salmon (1970) wherein population density of another member of Alpheidae, *Alpheus heterochaelis* (Say 1818), was highest in early summer but became scarce after the end of July. On another note, population density in Alpheid shrimps also have a role in mate-guarding behavior of such species, this was according to the study of Mathews (2002). This study of Mathews (2002) further emphasizes that since low and high population density affects mate-guarding behavior, therefore, the mate-guarding hypothesis for social monogamy predicts that males should change their guarding behavior in response to changes in population density.

Alpheus macellarius are known to inhabit mangrove areas where they form their burrows, as supported by Barba, Raz-Guzman and Sanchez (2005) that Caridean shrimps are numerically dominant in vegetated substrates. Clarin is one of the coastal municipalities in Bohol with a 7.5-hectare mangrove area. Distribution data of *A. macellarius* in Barangays Tangaran and Nahawan will provide an idea on the presence and absence of this species as well as the use of a particular type of habitat by the species (Barba, Raz-Guzman and Sanchez, 2005). Distribution data from this study will open the idea of using *A. macellarius* as an indicator species for particular environmental characteristics. And at the same time, it can be used especially for the species conservation plan (Franklin and Miller, 2010) of the municipality. Alpheid shrimps, according to Corfield and Alexander (1995), have a wide distribution, some of them occur in deep water, few in freshwater, while most are found in coral reefs, seagrass beds and the littoral zone. In the study of Homer and Heilskov (2008), the distribution of *A. macellarius* in the Bolinao area, Pangasinan was reduced to 60% as an impact of milkfish farming. Another study on distribution is by Hendrickx and Hermoso-Salazar (2005) on four species of *Alpheus* along the Pacific Coast of Mexico and they found out that *A. bellimanus* and *A. cristulifrons* have specific preferences in terms of depth, sediment composition, epibenthic water temperature and dissolved oxygen content of their ideal habitat.

The biomass measurement of *Alpheus macellarius* is also important in assessing stocks and for future fisheries management activities. Mortality, either fishing or natural cause, can decrease population biomass,

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while reproduction and population growth can increase population biomass (Russell, 1931) as cited by Cadrin and Secor (2009). Company *et al.* (2004) in their study on the deep-sea decapod crustaceans in the Western and Central Mediterranean Sea, aimed to compare the decapod biomass, species composition and population characteristics. Furthermore, species abundance and biomass were calculated both in number and in g/km^2 of the study area. This study then revealed that the decapod crustaceans and fishes were the dominant megafaunal groups in terms of total biomass and total abundance. The decrease of the species number, total decapod biomass and abundance with regards to the depth was also observed.

CHAPTER II MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. The Study Site

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Figure 1. Map of the Municipality of Clarin, Bohol in Central Philippines showing the location of the study site, Tangaran (blue box) and Nahawan (red box).

Municipality of Clarin, Bohol lies at $9^{\circ} 57' 43''$ North and $124^{\circ} 1' 25''$ East. It is located in the northeastern part of Bohol (Figure 1). It is a fifth class municipality composed of 24 barangays. Clarin has a total of 388 hectares of mangrove forest to where *A. macellarius* inhabits. There are six (6) coastal barangays in Clarin: Buacao, Lajog, Bonbon, Poblacion Norte, Tangaran and Nahawan. The latter two barangays (Tangaran and Nahawan) are the chosen sites of this study because it has the largest mangrove area in Clarin (CRM Plan of Clarin 2013-2017) and it is where *A. macellarius* are known to reside according to collectors. These barangays are sources of many marine products such as dried and fresh fish, and invertebrates.

2.2. Sampling

Figure 2. An illustration of how radial transect method was done.

Data were gathered through the radial transect method (Figure 2) (Mendoza, 2007). Sampling was done in two (2) mangrove areas of Clarin, Bohol: Tangaran and Nahawan. Sampling started in December 2016 and commended in May 2017, a total of six (6) months sampling period only because of time and financial constraints. In each sampling site, three random (3) 25 x 2 m radial transects were laid. Sampling took place 5 days before or after the onset of the full moon. The possibility of sampling bias cannot be disregarded since samples were collected based on the best sampling time according to collectors. (Disclaimer: This information were from the collectors' point of view only and did not have a scientific basis as of the moment). There was no observed specific time for collection since collectors would depend on the tide, and would prefer low tide as the best collection time.

2.3. Density, Biomass and Distribution

Density, biomass and distribution pattern were determined after collection. Density was computed as a number of individuals per m^2 by dividing the total number of individuals from each site by the area ($100 m^2$) of the radial transects. In the case of biomass, it was computed as grams per m^2 by dividing the total weight of collected individuals in each transect to the area of the radial transects (Company *et al.*, 2004). Bodyweight (W) was measured as wet weight using a digital weighing scale to the nearest 0.1g (Figure 3).

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Figure 3. Weighing of *Alpheus macellarius* to determine body weight (BW) in grams.

Distribution of the organism was computed using the Morisita's index:

$$= \frac{S (\Sigma n^2) - N}{N (N - 1)}$$

Where:

n= total number of individuals collected per collector,

N=total number of individuals collected by the collectors and

S= total number of collectors.

I=1 for a random distribution (i.e. variance = mean), 0 for a uniform distribution, and >1 for aggregated distribution (Bakus, 1990).

2.4. Statistical Analysis

Two-way factorial ANOVA was used in understanding if there was an interaction between barangays, within months and in between barangay and months for data on density and biomass. For density, the computed density value was the dependent variable and months and sites (barangays) were the independent variables. For biomass, the computed biomass was the dependent variable and months and sites (barangays) were the independent variables. Bonferroni test was used as a post hoc test for the 2 way factorial ANOVA.

CHAPTER III RESULTS

3.1. Density

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Figure 4. Density (ind/m²) of *A. macellarius* in Barangay Nahawan in a six months sampling period from December 2016 to May 2017 (N=250), indicating standard deviation (SD) each sampling month.

Mean density of *Alpheus macellarius* in Nahawan is 0.14 ind/m² of which it is highest during the month of February with 0.19 ind/m² and lowest during December with 0.10 ind/m² (Figure 4). Density values in the month of March have the largest standard deviation of 0.07 which means that the data set in the said month is more varied compared to other months of collection. December has the lowest standard deviation of 0.01 which means density values in this month are less varied than others.

Figure 5. Density (ind/m²) of *A. macellarius* in Barangay Tangaran in a six months sampling period from December 2016 to May 2017 (N=454), indicating standard deviation (SD) each sampling month.

Alpheus macellarius in barangay Tangaran has a mean density value of 0.26 ind/m², the month of December having the highest mean density of 0.44 ind/m² and lowest in April with 0.13 ind/m² (Figure 5). Density values in the month of February are the farthest from its mean density as reflected on its large standard deviation compared to other months which means that there is a large variety of data recorded in the said month. Contradictory to February, the smallest variation, as also reflected in its small standard deviation, was observed in the month of April.

Two-way factorial ANOVA yielded a significant difference in the density in between barangays Nahawan and Tangaran (df=1; $F=31.936$; $P<0.05$), and within months from December to May (df=5; $F=6.584$;

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$P < 0.05$). However, it was also found out that there is an interaction between sites and months ($df=5$; $F=6.234$; $P < 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 1. Two-way factorial ANOVA table of the density values of *A. macellarius* in Nahawan and Tangaran.

Source	Type III SS	df	Mean Squares	F-ratio	p-value
SITES	0.127	1	0.127	31.936	*0.000
MONTHS	0.131	5	0.026	6.584	*0.001
MONTHS*SITES	0.124	5	0.025	6.234	*0.001
Error	0.096	24	0.004		

* Significant at the $< .05$ level.

3.2. Biomass

Figure 6. Biomass (g/m^2) of *A. macellarius* in Barangay Nahawan in a six months sampling period from December 2016 to May 2017, indicating standard deviation (SD) each sampling month.

Individuals of *Alpheus macellarius* in Nahawan has a biomass value of $2.13 g/m^2$. The highest biomass value was observed during the month of February with $3.23 g/m^2$ and lowest in the month of December with $1.12 g/m^2$ (Figure 6). Standard deviation also shows that the greatest variation of data collected was in the month of January ($SD=1.09$) and the least variation was observed in the month of December ($SD=0.13$).

Figure 7. Biomass (g/m^2) of *A. macellarius* in Barangay Tangaran in a six months sampling period from December 2016 to May 2017, indicating standard deviation (SD) each sampling month.

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Collected samples of *A. macellarius* in Tangaran have higher biomass of 3.57 g/m², than Nahawan, with the month of December having the highest biomass value of 5.81 g/m² and lowest in the month of April with 1.57 g/m² (Figure 7). Standard deviation, as reflected in Figure 8 above, shows that the largest variation of the biomass data collection occurs in the month of February (SD=3.21) and lowest in the month of April (SD=1.57).

Two-way factorial ANOVA resulted to a significant difference in between barangay (df=1; $F=19.064$; $P<0.05$), within months (df=5; $F=5.558$; $P<0.05$). The same as to that of density, there is also an interaction between sites and months in the biomass values (df=5; $F=4.046$, $P<0.05$) (Table 2).

Table 2. Two-way factorial ANOVA table of the biomass values of *A. macellarius* in Nahawan and Tangaran.

Source	Type III SS	df	Mean Squares	F-ratio	p-value
SITES	0.469	1	0.469	19.064	*0.000
MONTHS	0.684	5	0.137	5.558	*0.002
MONTHS*SITES	0.498	5	0.100	4.046	*0.008
Error	0.591	24	0.025		

*Significant at the <0.05 level

3.3. Distribution

Using Morisita's Index of Dispersion, the data revealed that in barangay Nahawan *A. macellarius* is both aggregated and random in distribution. Samples from December, February and April are aggregated in distribution ($I>1$) and collected samples for January, March and May were randomly distributed ($I=1$). For barangay Tangaran, collected samples of *A. macellarius* are distributed aggregately ($I>1$) in the six months sampling period.

CHAPTER IV DISCUSSION

The density of *Alpheus macellarius* in Tangaran (0.26 ind/m²) and Nahawan (0.14 ind/m²) is within and above the range of the recorded density (0.20±0.03 ind/m²) of *A. macellarius* in the study of Palomar *et al.* (2004) in Bolinao Pangasinan, Philippines. Further, Palomar *et al.* (2004) in their study, recorded a significant difference in the density of *A. macellarius* across sites in which this study also revealed.

A significant difference in density (ind/m²) and biomass (g/ m²) was found between sites and within months, but there is an observed interaction between site and month. This means that the density and biomass of *Alpheus macellarius* in those sampling months (December – May) has something to do with the sites. This could probably be because of the organism's adaptation to the environmental condition of the site, since according to Palomar *et al.* (2005) that *A. macellarius* has the ability to respond to the different environmental conditions as evidenced in their burrow construction modification and adaptations in burrowing and feeding. This environmental condition could be the organic content load in each site. *A. macellarius* are burrowing organisms and that according to Palomar *et al.* (2005) their complex burrow shapes implies that deposit-feeding is the predominant feeding habit, they are also scavengers and suspension feeders, thus there is a greater possibility of this species to acquire organic content load or a part of their food supply coming from or contributed by human inhabitants near mangrove area. To corroborate, Palomar *et al.* (2005) in their study of *A. macellarius* behavior, stated that organic content, together with other physical factors, is important in ecological studies of burrowing organisms since their dependence on the sediment may strongly influence population and community structure. According to Payne and Finnegan (2006), nutrient availability together with primary productivity, is hypothesized to contribute to total biomass in the marine realm and that biomass also depends on factors such as food supply. It was personally observed that transects laid randomly during the six-month sampling period in Tangaran were just a few meters away from residences, while in Barangay Nahawan their mangrove area is a good 100 meters or more, away from residences, there could possibly be a difference in organic load. Solid wastes were very much visible in almost all corners of the mangrove area in Tangaran compared to Nahawan where it is noticeably lesser and infrequent. Collectors would also often complain about

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how smelly and dirty the mangrove area of Tangaran. This study did not include organic content analysis, thus warrants further studies to justify the idea of the organic content difference for both sites.

There is an observed decline of density and biomass during the months of April and May for both sites, which may be attributed to the temperature rise during summer months, a statement which was according to the collectors. To elaborate, collectors find it hard to capture *Alpheus macellarius* when their burrows are dried up due to the intense heat because, according to them, the organisms would hide to the deeper part of their burrows. This further is supported by the study of Palomar *et al.* (2005) that *A. macellarius* were often resting, inactive, or hidden during midday, possibly as a response to elevated temperature.

Aggregated and random distribution were observed in barangay Nahawan while *Alpheus macellarius* in Tangaran are aggregately distributed only. Thompson (2004) included environmental disturbance among the physical parameters that influence the pattern of distribution. If to compare by personal observation, Tangaran is more disturbed than Nahawan. Even if Nahawan is a barangay known to where the majority of the "takla" collectors reside and a populated area, but their mangrove area where they would frequently visit for collection is located far from residences than the mangrove area in Tangaran as per stated above. The sediment characteristics may also be another reason for the difference in distribution patterns in both sites. Rufino *et al.* (2006) in their study, mentioned how sediment characteristics play a role in the distribution of many benthic decapod crustacean especially those with burrowing or burying habit, of which *A. macellarius* belongs.

CHAPTER V CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion:

Density and biomass suggested an interaction between site and months when subjected to two-way factorial ANOVA. There was also a significant difference between sites and within sampling months. This is probably because of the difference in environmental conditions in both sites, since *Alpheus macellarius* mode of feeding can be easily influenced by the different environmental conditions. The organic content load could be another affecting factor, since base on personal observation, waste management is poor in Tangaran than in Nahawan.

Alpheus macellarius in Nahawan are aggregately and randomly distributed, on the other hand, the said organism is aggregately distributed in Tangaran. Environmental disturbances and different sediment characteristics are the possible cause of such difference in distribution patterns.

Recommendations:

1. The mode of feeding of *Alpheus macellarius* as a burrowing organism can be influenced by different environmental conditions (e.g. sediment characteristics, organic content). Organic matter (OM) analysis shall be taken into consideration to further shed light on the relationship of density, biomass and distribution to such aspects.
2. As organic matter (OM) analysis is suggested, it is but fitting also that gut content analysis of the species may be considered to clarify its food component breakdown.
3. As previously mentioned that there was no municipal ordinance on the regulation of collecting such species, it is also recommended that higher authorities may consider drafting a municipal ordinance since it was also found out (based on the interview) that there are foreign collectors (collectors coming from other municipalities).
4. To get a good representation of *Alpheus macellarius* data on other months not covered in this study, it is then suggested that another study shall be conducted at least 1 year as a minimum of the sampling period.

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